

TECHNICAL SCIENCES

IMPROVING THE METHODOLOGY FOR ASSESSING THE READINESS OF AN INFORMATION SECURITY SYSTEM FOR A CRITICAL INFORMATION INFRASTRUCTURE FACILITY

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Abstract

Today, security is no longer limited to the installation of a single device, and must be ensured at the level of each package, service, or component of a critical information infrastructure facility. Information security measures must be distributed throughout the working environment of a critical information infrastructure facility and must support the following conditions: availability and reliability of services, continuity of business operations, and a specified level of system service and efficiency. The creation of securely protected critical information infrastructure facilities is an all-encompassing dilemma, which includes: ensuring the confidentiality of information that is stored, processed and transmitted through communication channels; ensuring access control to information resources of critical information infrastructure facilities in accordance with user authority, as well as the integrity and identification of stored and transmitted information; preventing information leakage, information circulating in critical information infrastructure facilities; exclusion of unauthorized access to information during its storage and processing in critical information infrastructure facilities, as well as prevention of software impacts or their consequences causing information distortion or destruction; implementation of necessary organizational and technical measures to ensure information security of critical information infrastructure facilities.

Keywords: an object of critical information infrastructure, infrastructure protection, information security, comprehensive security systems, unauthorized access to information.

As of September 1, 2025, amendments to the Federal Law "On the Security of the Russian Federation's Critical Information Infrastructure" come into force. The new requirements aim to strengthen technological independence and enhance the security of critical infrastructure facilities. In connection with the development of lists of typical industry-specific critical infrastructure facilities, it has been clarified that these lists are established by the Government of the Russian Federation. The innovations also suggest that the Russian Government will establish:

- industry - specific features of categorizing critical infrastructure facilities, which determine the procedure for setting criteria of significance and indicators of their values for critical infrastructure facilities, as well as the procedure for calculating values taking into account the characteristics of critical infrastructure facilities - jointly with the FSTEC of Russia, and for financial sector organizations jointly with the Central Bank of the Russian Federation;

- requirements for software and hardware used at significant critical infrastructure facilities - for financial sector organizations jointly with the Central Bank of the Russian Federation.

Until such lists and sectoral specifics are approved, critical infrastructure entities must follow the general procedure for categorizing critical

infrastructure facilities established by Government Decree No. 127 dated February 8, 2018, "On Approval of the Rules for Categorizing Critical Information Infrastructure Facilities in the Russian Federation, as well as a List of Criteria for Assessing the Significance of Critical Information Infrastructure Facilities in the Russian Federation and Their Values."

The new regulations also eliminated the time limit for returning submitted information about critical infrastructure facilities, as previously, the Federal Service for Technical and Export Control was required to review the information within 10 days. It is also excluded that the information will be returned due to an unreasonably assigned significance category, as it is assumed that the documents planned for development on assigning significance categories, taking into account industry-specific features, will eliminate such inaccuracies in calculating the categories. The text of the federal law in question strengthens the requirements for technological independence, and it is assumed that the Government of the Russian Federation must establish:

- the procedure and deadlines for switching to the use of the required software and hardware products and domestic software;

- the procedure for monitoring the use of the required software and hardware products and domestic software.

At the same time, there is a separate instruction

that gives the right to the Government of the Russian Federation to establish a special procedure for applying the above-mentioned norms in certain territories of the Russian Federation.

As of today, the Presidential Decree No. 250 dated May 1, 2022, prohibits the use of information security products manufactured in "unfriendly" countries, regardless of the category of importance of the critical infrastructure facility.

At the same time, for CII entities that are customers under Federal Law No. 223-FZ of 18 July 2011, Presidential Decree No. 166 of 30 March 2022 additionally prohibits the use of foreign software at significant critical infrastructure facilities.

For other CII entities that are not subject to Presidential Decree No. 166, there are currently no federal requirements for the import substitution of software and hardware that are not classified as information security tools. [1]

References

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